

Simple correlations for the π -electron energy and other properties of cata-condensed benzenoids[†]

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Abstract : In continuation of previous investigations, it is now shown that for catafusenes the Hückel π -electron energy is correlated excellently with two simple descriptors (small integers), namely the number h of benzenoid rings and the number n of zeros in the code of their dualists, i.e. the number of linearly fused rings. On the other hand, several bulk physical properties of cata-condensed benzenoids (such as the normal boiling point, the chromatographic retention index, the logarithm of the water solubility, the octanol-water partition coefficient) and one molecular property (the heat of formation), may be correlated satisfactorily with h and/or topological indices.

Keywords : Benzenoids, Hückel π -electron energy, dualists, topological index, physical properties, regression analysis.

Introduction

In a previous paper¹ it was shown that several physical properties of cata-condensed polycyclic benzenoid hydrocarbons (benzenoid catafusenes) could be satisfactorily accounted for by biparametric correlations involving two small integers : the number h of hexagonal rings and the number $n + 1$, where n is the number of zeros in the dualist code of the benzenoid. In an earlier paper² it had been shown that the condensation geometry of catafusenes, expressed by the parameter $(n + 1)$, also influenced their half-wave reduction potentials and their reaction rates in Diels-Alder cycloadditions with maleic anhydride.

A few explanations are necessary at this point about *dualists of benzenoids* (inner duals) and the codes of

catafusenes. Benzenoid dualists are composed of vertices (centers of hexagons in a benzenoid) and edges that connect vertices corresponding to condensed rings, i.e. rings sharing a CC bond. Unlike normal molecular graphs, where bond angles and bond lengths do not matter, bond angles play an important role in dualists. If the benzenoid is considered to be a portion of the hexagonal lattice (honeycomb grid), the dualist is a part of the triangular lattice. Dualists allow the classification of benzenoids into catafusenes, perifusenes, and coronoids according to whether the dualist contains no cycles, 3-membered rings, or larger rings, respectively. Catafusenes with h benzenoid rings obey Erich Hückel's aromaticity rule with $4k + 2$ π -electrons (where k is a small non-negative integer), are isomeric, and have the formula $C_hH_{(h+6)/2}$.

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

The geometry of catafusenes can be uniquely mirrored by a code wherein, starting from one end of the longest path, an angle of 180° between successive edges is symbolized by 0, and kinked angles of 120° or 240° are symbolized by 1 or 2 for "left-turn" or "right-turn"; branching is symbolized by a pair of brackets enclosing the code of the branch, with (.) symbolizing a branch involving one benzenoid ring; the smallest number is selected as the canonical code among all resulting combinations of digits 0, 1, and 2. Table 1 present dualists of catafusenes and their canonical codes. Usually codes are enclosed in square brackets, but these brackets will be dispensed with in the present paper.

Catafusenes whose codes differ only by interchanging digits 1 with 2 are quite similar in many topological properties, and are called *isoarithmic* because they have a one-to-one correspondence between their resonance (Kekulé) structures. In particular, their Hückel π -electron energies are equal. However, when steric interactions lead to non-planarity, as in the case of helicenes, the properties of such systems differ considerably from those of isarithmic planar benzenoids such as the zigzag catafusenes.

Table-1 (contd.)

Table 1. Data for catafusenes 1-82 and their π -electron energies

No.	<i>h</i>	<i>n</i> + 1	code	E_{π}	Structure
1	2	1		13.6832	
2	3	2	0	19.3137	
3	3	1	1	19.4483	
4	4	3	00	24.9308	
5	4	2	01	25.1012	
6	4	1	12	25.1875	
7	4	1	11	25.1922	
8	4	1	1(.)	25.2745	
9	5	4	000	30.5401	
10	5	3	001	30.7256	

11	5	3	010	30.7627	
12	5	2	011	30.8338	
13	5	2	012	30.8390	
14	5	2	101	30.8795	
15	5	2	102	30.8805	
16	5	1	111	30.9362	
17	5	1	112	30.9386	
18	5	2	01(.)	30.9418	
19	5	1	121	30.9432	
20	5	1	11(.)	30.9990	
21	6	5	0000	36.1560	
22	6	4	0001	36.3413	
23	6	4	0010	36.3905	
24	6	3	0011	36.4562	
25	6	3	0012	36.4613	
26	6	3	0110	36.4783	
27	6	3	0120	36.4839	

Table-1 (contd.)

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28	6	3	1001	36.5169							
29	6	3	1002	36.5172							
30	6	3	0101	36.5378							
31	6	2	0102	36.5390							
32	6	3	001(.)	36.5705							
33	6	2	0111	36.5864							
34	6	2	0112	36.5874							
35	6	2	0122	36.5924							
36	6	3	01(.)0	36.6140							
37	6	2	1011	36.6152							
38	6	2	1022	36.6165							
39	6	2	1210	36.6198							
40	6	2	1012	36.6198							
41	6	1	1021	36.6209							

Table-1 (contd)

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56	6	1	121()	36 7552							
57	6	1	1()1()	36 7953							
58	7	6	00000	41 7675							
59	7	5	00001	41 9542							
60	7	5	00100	42 0201							
61	7	4	00120	42 1057							
62	7	4	10002	42 1374							
63	7	4	0001()	42 1875							
64	7	4	01(0)0	42 2903							
65	7	3	1001()	42 3598							
66	7	2	01111	42 4300							
67	7	1	12121	42 4415							
68	7	2	1()01()	42 5461							
69	7	1	11111	42 7638							

Correlations between π -electron energy and two simple topological descriptors, h and $n + 1$

In Table 1 one can see the structures of 82 dualists of catafusenes with $h = 2$ to 10 benzenoid rings (denoted as 1–82) with their codes and Hückel π -electron energies. The number n of zeros in their codes is expressed as the parameter $n + 1$. Many of structures are isoarithmic, e.g. those with codes 11 and 12; 101 and 102; 111, 112, and 121; etc.

Because for each h value the E_π values are clustered close to each other, the monoparametric correlation

$$E_\pi = 2.3270 + 5.7070 (\pm 0.0124) h \quad (1)$$

has a very high coefficient $R^2 = 0.9996$. Other statistical parameters are :

$N = 82$ structures, CV (coefficient of variation) = 0.0043, F (Fisher parameter) = 11460.1.

However, at constant h values, one can see that the parameter $n + 1$ also explains some of the variance :

$$\text{for } h = 5 \text{ (12 catafusenes), } E_\pi = 31.101 - 0.1249(n + 1), R^2 = 0.886; \quad (2)$$

$$\text{for } h = 6 \text{ (37 catafusenes), } E_\pi = 36.839 - 0.1150(n + 1), R^2 = 0.850; \quad (3)$$

$$\text{for } h = 7 \text{ (12 catafusenes), } E_\pi = 42.679 - 0.1335(n + 1), R^2 = 0.853. \quad (4)$$

Therefore we consider that the best correlation using two simple (small integer) topological descriptors for catafusenes is the biparametric equation :

$$E_\pi = 2.5393 + 5.7620 (\pm 0.0059)h - 0.1095 (\pm 0.0056)(n + 1) \quad (5)$$

where $N = 82$, $R^2 = 0.9999$, CV = 0.0018, F = 99539.3.

Correlations between physical properties and topological indices

In the previous paper¹ several physical properties of catafusenes were discussed, and correlated with the same two parameters as in the foregoing section, namely h and $n + 1$. Four of these are *molecular properties* that are almost independent of the aggregation state and depend mainly on the topology of the molecule, i.e. on n : (1) energies of the p -band (1L_b -band) in electronic absorp-

tion spectra (ΔE_p); (2) ionization potentials (IP); (3) electron affinities (EA); (4) HOMO-LUMO gap (E -gap, in eV; or hardness H , in β units). Then, five *bulk properties* that depend mainly on h and are manifest in condensed phase (usually liquid phase, because in crystalline phase the direction-specific intermolecular packing forces add further complications); (5) normal boiling point (NBP, in $^\circ\text{C}$); (6) chromatographic retention index (RI); (7) the logarithm of the water solubility ($\log S$); (8) the logarithm of the lipophilicity measured by the octanol-water partition coefficient ($\log K_{ow}$); and (9) heat (enthalpy) of formation from elements in standard condition (ΔH_f , in kJ/mol). Now we wish to investigate whether one may find correlations between some of these properties and topological indices of catafusenes. Several books on topological indices are available³⁻⁸.

Table 2 presents (for the same 82 catafusenes that were displayed in the previous section) the above physical properties (where they are available), and several topological indices : the Wiener index (W), the first two connectivity indices (${}^1\chi$ and the Randić index ${}^2\chi$), the Balaban index J , which does not increase automatically with graph size, and a related index (G) which does⁹, the Padmakar-Ivan index PI, and the Szeged index Sz.

In Table 3 one can see intercorrelation factors R^2 between molecular descriptors (h and topological indices TIs) that were included in Table 2. Index J has negative R^2 values for intercorrelations with all other TIs. The highest R^2 value is between h and ${}^1\chi$, followed by h and ${}^2\chi$, Sz and PI, and then by ${}^1\chi$ and ${}^2\chi$ but, as indicated by Randić, in biparametric correlations even such cases may lead to valid conclusions¹¹⁻¹⁵. Randić^{11,12} stated that if a descriptor strongly correlates with another descriptor already used in a regression, such a descriptor in most studies should be discarded. For example ${}^1\chi$ and ${}^2\chi$, ${}^1\chi$ often strongly correlate and in many structure-property-activity studies ${}^2\chi$ has been discarded. This is not theoretically justified and despite the widespread practice should be stopped. Although two highly correlated descriptors overall depict the same features of molecular structure, it is important to recognize that even highly interre-

Table 2. Physicochemical properties, codes and topological indices of benzimidazoles used in the present study

No.	h	Code	NBP	RI	log S	log K _{ow}	IP	EA	ΔH _f	E-gap	E _p	W	¹ χ	² χ	J	G	PI	Sz
1	2		218	2.00	1.49	3.33	8.57	0.33	150.6	8.24	4.38	109	4.966	4.089	1.925	44.423	96	243
2	3	0	340	3.20	-1.36	4.54	8.05	0.84	218.3	7.21	3.38	279	6.933	6.081	1.682	73.260	216	656
3	3	1	340	3.00	0.06	4.55	8.48	0.48	209.1	8.00	4.23	271	6.949	5.994	1.740	75.787	218	632
4	4	00	440	4.51	-2.82	5.96	7.72	1.19	286.1	6.54	2.71	569	8.899	8.072	1.465	103.187	384	1381
5	4	01	438	4.00	-2.03	5.91	8.11	0.83	276.9	7.28	3.53	553	8.916	7.986	1.512	106.497	388	1325
6	4	12	431	4.10	-24.6	5.84	8.26	0.72	267.7	7.54	3.87	529	8.933	7.909	1.587	111.780	390	1253
7	4	11		3.64	-2.46	5.84	8.28	0.69	280.5	7.59	3.84	545	8.933	7.909	1.538	108.329	390	1301
8	4	1(-)	425	3.70	-1.39	5.45	8.50	0.56	258.5	7.95	5.13	513	7.837	11.949	1.642	115.654	390	1269
9	5	000	529			7.19	7.50	1.43	353.9	6.07	2.23	1011	10.865	10.064	1.288	133.584	600	2506
10	5	001		4.99		6.81	7.80	1.15		6.65	2.83	987	10.882	9.977	1.321	137.007	606	2410
11	5	010		4.67		6.81	8.11	0.84	344.7	7.27	3.55	979	10.882	9.977	1.335	138.459	608	2378
12	5	011		4.33			7.97	0.97	348.3	7.01		939	10.899	9.900	1.395	144.681	610	2258
13	5	012	524	5.00		7.11	7.97	1.00	339	7.00	3.27	971	10.899	9.891	1.348	139.807	610	2354
14	5	101	524	4.56	-2.99	6.54	8.17	0.83	335.5	7.32	3.60	955	10.899	9.891	1.367	141.777	610	2290
15	5	102	524	4.73	-2.60	6.75	8.15	0.83	335.5	7.32	3.57	971	10.899	9.891	1.346	139.599	610	2354
16	5	111	519	4.07		7.11	8.22	0.82	333	7.35		899	10.916	9.824	1.461	151.527	612	2138
17	5	112	519	4.45		7.11	8.27	0.75	333.5	7.52		931	10.916	9.814	1.408	146.030	612	2234
18	5	01(-)	524	4.40		7.19	8.17	0.82	326.3	7.35	3.80	907	10.916	9.828	1.449	150.282	610	2290
19	5	121	519	5.18	-2.37	7.11	8.24	0.75	326.3	7.49		963	10.916	9.804	1.361	141.155	612	2330
20	5	11(-)		4.27			8.16	0.82	329.8	7.34		883	10.933	9.751	1.492	154.742	612	2202
21	6	0000					7.34	1.61		5.74	1.90	1637	12.832	12.055	1.145	164.186	864	4119
22	6	0001					7.57	1.39	384.8	6.18	2.37	1605	12.848	11.969	1.169	167.628	872	3975
23	6	0010									2.94	1589	12.848	11.969	1.184	169.778	876	3903
24	6	0011									2.72	1533	12.865	11.892	1.228	176.088	878	3735
25	6	0012							406.8			1581	12.865	11.882	1.190	170.639	878	3879
26	6	0110					7.82	1.16		6.66	3.02	1509	12.865	11.892	1.251	179.386	880	3655
27	6	0120					7.87	1.11		6.77	2.95	1637	12.832	12.055	1.145	164.186	880	3847
28	6	1001					7.87	1.11		6.77	2.95	1565	12.865	11.882	1.199	171.929	878	3799
29	6	1002					7.87	1.11		6.76	2.95	1581	12.865	11.882	1.188	170.352	878	3879
30	6	0101									3.42	1541	12.865	11.882	1.221	175.084	880	3719
31	6	0102										1573	12.865	11.882	1.197	171.643	832	3399
32	6	001(-)					7.85	1.13		6.72		1485	12.882	11.820	1.271	182.254	878	3783
33	6	0111										1453	12.882	11.815	1.301	186.556	834	3039
34	6	0112										1501	12.882	11.806	1.258	180.390	882	3631

Table-2 (contd.)

70	8	000120	3457	16.798	15.865	0.968	234.211	1564	8577
71	8	001200	3449	16.798	15.865	0.971	234.937	1566	8537
72	8	001(0)00	3161	16.815	15.803	1.066	257.922	1988	11134
73	8	001(0)0	3057	16.815	15.803	1.105	267.359	1990	10814
74	8	121212	3401	16.865	15.519	0.987	238.808	1578	8377
75	8	1(0)001(0)	3073	16.865	15.567	1.088	263.245	1572	7913
76	8	111111	3201	17.227	15.169	1.042	252.116	1572	7681
77	9	0001200	4787	18.764	17.857	0.886	266.538	1990	12904
78	9	001(0)00	4195	18.781	17.794	1.020	306.850	1982	11518
79	9	1(0)0001(0)	4347	18.832	17.559	0.970	291.808	1988	11182
80	9	1111111	4315	19.157	17.020	0.962	289.402	1994	10342
81	10	001(00)00	5541	20.747	19.786	0.954	349.272	1980	11048
82	10	11111111	5821	21.123	19.018	0.902	330.234	2464	13787

lated descriptors differ in some other structural traits. The difference between them may be relatively small but nevertheless it may be very important for structure-property regression.

The criteria for inclusion or exclusion of descriptors should not be based on parallelism between descriptors even if overwhelming, but should be based on whether the part in which two descriptors disagree is or is not relevant for the characterization of the property considered. If the part in which the second descriptor differs from the first, regardless of how small it is, is relevant for the property under consideration, then the descriptor should be included. Randić^{11,12} further stated that the selection of descriptors to be used in structure-property-activity studies should not be delegated solely to computers, although statistical criteria will continue to be useful for preliminary screening of descriptors taken from a large pool. Often in an automated selection of descriptors, a descriptor will be discarded because it is highly correlated with another descriptor already selected. But what is important is not whether two descriptors parallel one another; i.e. duplicate much of the same structural information, but whether they are complementary in those parts that are important for structure-property-activity correlations. Hence, the residual of the correlation between two descriptors should be examined and kept or discarded depending on how well it can improve the correlation based on already selected descriptors.

In monoparametric correlations, the hardness led to correlation coefficients $R^2 < 0.58$ for all the indices listed in Table 2; for IP, EA, E -gap, and ΔE_p , only index J led to R^2 values between 0.59 and 0.67, which are still too low for significant correlations. In the previous paper¹ it

was concluded that, for such "molecular (intrinsic) physical properties", most of the variance is explained by parameter $n + 1$ characterizing the longest acenic portion(s) of the benzenoid, whereas for bulk properties the number h of benzenoid rings explains most of the variance.

One should note that the number h of benzenoid rings correlates well (with $R^2 > 0.9$) with $\log K_{ow}$ ($R^2 = 0.9743$), ΔH_f ($R^2 = 0.9818$), and NBP ($R^2 = 0.9934$), in monoparametric correlations. With all other physical properties from Table 2, h does not show any correlation with $R^2 > 0.9$.

Therefore in the following we shall examine only the remaining four "bulk physical properties", NBP, RI, $\log S$, $\log K_{ow}$, and one "molecular physical property" ΔH_f , for which several indices give in monoparametric correlations values $R^2 > 0.9$. More precisely, for RI, only index J has $R^2 > 0.9$; for $\log K_{ow}$ such $R^2 > 0.9$ values are obtained for ${}^1\chi$, PI, W , and Sz (in decreasing order); for ΔH_f such $R^2 > 0.9$ values are obtained for ${}^1\chi$, W , and J (in decreasing order); for NBP, such $R^2 > 0.9$ values are obtained for ${}^1\chi$, PI, W , Sz , and J (in decreasing order); and no topological index was able to correlate with $R^2 > 0.9$ with $\log S$.

We investigated then biparametric correlations between the above four remaining bulk physical properties and h with one of the topological indices, or two topological indices. In addition to R^2 , CV and the F statistical parameters, we will also include the adjusted R^2A coefficient. Starting with biparametric correlations involving h and one topological index, Table 4 presents the highest correlation coefficients in such QSPR. In each case, the top

Table 3. Intercorrelation matrix of molecular descriptors (h and topological indices)

	W	${}^1\chi$	${}^2\chi$	J	G	PI	Sz	h
W	1							
${}^1\chi$	0.9518	1						
${}^2\chi$	0.9456	0.9773	1					
J	-0.8529	-0.9205	-0.9075	1				
G	0.4250	0.4288	0.3777	-0.3283	1			
PI	0.9621	0.9658	0.9537	-0.8561	0.4236	1		
Sz	0.9698	0.9369	0.9335	-0.8348	0.3716	0.9884	1	
h	0.9532	0.9989	0.9859	-0.9217	0.4139	0.9664	0.9392	1

value (boldface characters) is a better correlation than that indicated previously¹ in biparametric correlations involving the two small integers h and $n + 1$.

Table 4. Biparametric correlations involving h and one TI

Property	Parameters	R^2	R^2A	CV	F	
NBP	h, PI	0.9980	0.9917	0.0098	3013.6	
	h, G	0.9954	0.9947	0.0150	1307.9	
	h, J	0.9953	0.9946	0.0151	1278.6	
	h, W	0.9951	0.9943	0.0155	1224.6	
	h, Sz	0.9949	0.9940	0.0158	1167.0	
RI	h, J	0.9246	0.9152	0.0542	98.1	
log S	h, PI	0.8799	0.8499	-0.3098	29.3	
	h, Sz	0.8500	0.8124	-0.3462	22.7	
log K_{ow}	$h, 2\chi$	0.9799	0.9764	0.0292	373.9	
	$h, 1\chi$	0.9793	0.9767	0.0292	377.7	
	h, J	0.9746	0.9714	0.0322	306.4	
	h, G	0.9745	0.9713	0.0322	305.4	
	h, PI	0.9745	0.9714	0.0322	306.3	
	h, W	0.9744	0.9712	0.0323	304.0	
	h, Sz	0.9744	0.9712	0.0322	305.0	
	ΔH_f	h, J	0.9856	0.9842	0.0258	685.3
		$h, 1\chi$	0.9843	0.9828	0.0270	628.6
		$h, 2\chi$	0.9842	0.9826	0.0271	622.9
h, G		0.9828	0.9811	0.0283	571.3	
h, Sz		0.9828	0.9811	0.0282	572.1	
	h, PI	0.9825	0.9808	0.0285	562.0	
	h, W	0.9821	0.9803	0.0288	549.7	

The Padmakar-Ivan index, PI, in association with h provides the best biparametric correlation with NBP; the Balaban J index in association with h provides the best biparametric correlation with RI and ΔH_f .

Next we will present biparametric correlations between the same bulk physical properties and two topological indices (TIs), as seen in Table 5. The highest R^2 value is written for each property in boldface characters.

It can be seen from Table 5 that index J is present in all correlations involving the retention index (RI), in agreement with Table 4 and with the result of the mono-parametric correlations; together, indices J and G (which are related but poorly intercorrelated), lead to a higher R^2 value for RI than all other correlations. However, for the other bulk physical properties, the R^2 values from Table 5 are lower than those displayed in Table 4 for biparametric correlations involving one TI and the number h of benzenoid rings. It is nevertheless remarkable that 1χ and 2χ are present in many biparametric correlations.

Table 5. Biparametric correlations between bulk physical properties and two TIs

Property	Parameters	R^2	R^2A	CV	F
NBP	$1\chi, 2\chi$	0.9937	0.9926	0.0176	939.9
	G, Sz	0.9929	0.9918	0.0186	844.9
	$1\chi, G$	0.9901	0.9885	0.0220	600.5
RI	J, G	0.9270	0.9179	0.0539	101.6
	W, J	0.9251	0.9158	0.0545	98.5
	$1\chi, J$	0.9246	0.9152	0.0547	98.1
	J, Sz	0.9246	0.9152	0.0547	98.1
	J, PI	0.9245	0.9150	0.0548	97.9
log S	W, J	0.8831	0.8539	-0.3055	30.2
	J, Sz	0.8831	0.8539	-0.3056	30.2
log K_{ow}	$1\chi, G$	0.9798	0.9773	0.0286	388.5
	$1\chi, 2\chi$	0.9794	0.9768	0.0290	380.0
	$1\chi, PI$	0.9766	0.9737	0.0308	333.9
	$W, 1\chi$	0.9764	0.9735	0.0310	331.3
	$1\chi, Sz$	0.9761	0.9731	0.0312	326.5
ΔH_f	$1\chi, 2\chi$	0.9845	0.9829	0.0269	633.8
	$1\chi, J$	0.9839	0.9822	0.0274	609.4
	$1\chi, PI$	0.9824	0.9807	0.0286	558.6
	$1\chi, Sz$	0.9824	0.9807	0.0286	558.7

At this point it will be interesting to comment on R^2A values. They take into account of adjustment of R^2 . Therefore, if a variable is added that does not contribute its fair share, the R^2A will actually decline. It is worth mentioning that R^2A is a measure of the % explained variation in the dependent variable that takes into account the relationship between the number of cases and the number of independent variables in the regression model. Furthermore, R^2A takes into account the relationship between sample size and number of variables used; R^2 may appear artificially high if the number of variables is high compared to the sample size.

Conclusions :

For 82 catafusenes with $h = 2$ to 10 benzenoid rings, the variance of E_π (the Hückel π -electron energy) is explained to a large extent by the number h of benzenoid rings; in addition, another small integer (the number n of linearly fused rings, corresponding to zeros in the code of the dualists) provides additional information for isomeric catafusenes. For four "bulk physical properties", namely normal boiling point (NBP), chromatographic retention index (RI), water solubility (log S), and lipophilicity (log K_{ow}) as well as one "molecular physical

property”, the enthalpy of formation from elements in standard conditions (ΔH_f) we found that correlations in terms of several molecular descriptors (h and a few topological indices such as the Padmakar-Ivan index PI, the Balaban index J and its newer relative G , as well as the Randić index ${}^2\chi$, are sometimes able to provide better biparametric correlations than the couple of small simple integers h and n .

The Padmakar-Ivan index was calculated using PADMONA software, whereas all other topological indices were calculated using the DRAGON software.

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